

A Study on Etiology, Clinical Profile and Outcome of Acute Pancreatitis in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Uttar Pradesh, India**Rahul Poddar¹, Richa Jha², Kartikey Prakash³**^{1,2,3}Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, GS Medical College and Hospital, Pilkhuwa, Uttar Pradesh

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Surgeons worldwide treat acute pancreatitis, a complicated illness with a wide range of local and systemic consequences. Acute pancreatitis is a pancreatic inflammatory condition that can affect regional tissues to varied degrees. Our goal was to ascertain the prevalence, cause, and result of AP. The aetiology, clinical characteristics, and prognosis of acute pancreatitis in rural Uttar Pradesh have not been thoroughly studied before.

Materials and Methods: The study was done in the Department General surgery at GS Medical college pilkhuwa, Uttar Pradesh, India. The medical superintendent of this medical college granted permission to carry out this investigation. The institutional review board and ethical committee gave its approval. The Institutional Ethics Committee granted an exemption from evaluation because the researcher will not interact with the patient and the study merely entails reviewing hospital records. Case study forms were used to collect required data from the patient charts.

Results: Local complications, defined as the presence of acute peripancreatic fluid collection, pancreatic pseudocyst, pancreatic necrosis were observed in 41.6% of cases. Metabolic complications such as acidosis, hypoalbuminemia, hypocalcemia was present in 26.9% of cases. Organ involvement was present in 38.4% of cases and the most common among them was respiratory system involvement.

Conclusion: In this article, the aetiology, clinical profile, and outcome of acute pancreatitis are described regionally for the first time. This might be a representation of the situation in emerging nations generally due to similarities in population and institutions. This will assist in creating a hospital policy that will be advantageous.

Keywords: Acute pancreatitis, Etiology, Clinical profile, pancreatic inflammatory condition.

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Introduction

Uncertainties about the pathophysiology and multi-organ involvement of the disease, uncertainty about outcome prediction, and a limited number of effective treatment modalities limit the ability to manage severe acute pancreatitis and deal with its clinical course. [1]

The main causes of acute pancreatitis are alcohol and gallstones. The third largest group (between 15 and 25 %) is idiopathic acute pancreatitis [2,3] (IAP). As the third most common cause of pancreatitis, IAP is therefore both clinically and socioeconomically highly relevant, but was often difficult to assess in terms of pancreatitis outcome due to varying definitions of the term "idiopathic" in previous studies. [4-6]

The proportion of actual idiopathic acute pancreatitis had been significantly overestimated in the pre-endosonography era were patients with EUS detected biliary etiology have been missed and

misclassified as idiopathic pancreatitis patients. [7] Due to the lack of uniform diagnostics in the context of pancreatitis etiology work-up and often ambiguous IAP inclusion and exclusion criteria (related to extended/repeated imaging such as CT, MRI, EUS, transabdominal ultrasound) as well as an unclear differentiation from the cohort of idiopathic recurrent acute pancreatitis/early chronic pancreatitis, the risk of adverse outcome in the third largest pancreatitis etiology group is so far unknown. [4,8]

Hypercalcemia may cause acute pancreatitis as a result of calcium deposition in the pancreatic duct and trypsinogen activation within the pancreatic parenchyma. Clinical characteristics and severity of acute pancreatitis with extra-pancreatic organ failure are systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) elicited by lesion of the acinar cells. [9]

Pancreatic auto-digestion is caused by the intra-pancreatic release of active pancreatic enzymes. This establishes a vicious cycle of active enzymes that damage acinar cells, vascular endothelium, and interstitium. [9] The warning signs of pancreatitis include tetany from hypocalcaemia, fulminant pancreatitis, Grey-Turner's and Cullen's signs, which indicate hemorrhagic pancreatitis, fever, which implies infection or inflammation, and hypovolemia.

One of the most important indicators of acute pancreatitis is fever. Inflammatory cytokines generated during the first week are the initial mediators. Infection of necrotic tissues may result in fever during the second or third week. Additionally, some people may develop pleural effusion. [10]

Standard abdominal discomfort, a three-fold increase in serum lipase or amylase levels, and confirmed findings from cross-sectional abdominal imaging are the basis for diagnosing acute pancreatitis. [11] The purpose of the current study was to assess the causes, symptoms, and consequences of acute pancreatitis in our community.

Materials and Methods

Study design and settings

Retrospective chart analysis revealed that this study was cross-sectional. Retrospective chart analysis of all acute pancreatitis cases from the previous ten years at this tertiary care facility with clinical, laboratory, and radiological data indicative of acute pancreatitis is the basis of this hospital-based investigation.

Study sample

Sample size was calculated as 456.

$$P = \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}; Q = 1 - P$$

2

Where,

P_1 – Anticipated proportion of event in group 1
 P_2 – Anticipated proportion of event in group 2
 d – Clinically significant difference ($P_1 - P_2$)

$$(Z_{1-\alpha}) = 1.96 \text{ (5\% } \alpha \text{ error)}$$

2

$$(Z_{1-\beta}) = 0.84 \text{ (80\% power)}$$

Study area

The study was done in the Department General surgery at GS Medical college pilkhuwa, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Study permission

The medical superintendent of this medical college granted permission to carry out this investigation. The institutional review board and ethical committee gave its approval.

The Institutional Ethics Committee granted an exemption from evaluation because the researcher will not interact with the patient and the study merely entails reviewing hospital records.

Study instruments

Case study forms were used to collect required data from the patient charts.

Inclusion criteria: The study comprised patients of any age who had radiographic (CECT abdomen), laboratory, and clinical signs of acute pancreatitis.

Exclusion criteria

Patients with chronic pancreatitis, those with other pancreatic diseases such as pancreatic cancers or cysts, those who had undergone prior pancreatic surgery, and those who were contraindicated for contrast-enhanced CT abdominal imaging (due to renal insufficiency, contrast allergy, pregnancy, etc.) were all excluded.

Data analysis: The data collected will be tabulated in SPSS software version 24 for analysis.

Results

Local complications, defined as the presence of acute peripancreatic fluid collection, pancreatic pseudocyst, pancreatic necrosis were observed in 41.6% of cases. Incidence of each complication is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Local complications

	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Acute fluid collection	132	28.9
None	263	57.6
Pancreatic necrosis	31	6.7
Pseudocyst	30	6.5
Total	456	100

Metabolic complications such as acidosis, hypoalbuminemia, hypocalcemia was present in 26.9% of cases (Table 2).

Table 2: Metabolic complications

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Acidosis	7	1.5
Hypercalcemia	5	1.0
Hypoalbuminemia	3	0.6
Hypocalcemia	123	26.9
None	318	69.7
Total	456	100

Organ involvement was present in 38.4% of cases and the most common among them was respiratory system involvement (Table 3).

Table 3: Organ involvement

	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Cardiac	11	2.4
Hematological (Hemorrhage, deranged INR)	8	1.7
MODS	55	12.0
Renal	34	7.4
Respiratory	76	16.6

Length of hospital stay exceeded 7 days in 47.3% of cases (Table 4).

Table 4: Length of hospital stay

	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Less than 7 days	240	52.6
More than 7 days	216	47.3
Total	456	100

Disease severity was mild in 80.0% of cases and severe in 5.4% of cases (Table 5).

Table 5: CT severity index

Severity	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Mild	365	80.0
Moderate	66	14.4
Severe	25	5.4
Total	456	100

Discussion

The most frequent gastrointestinal ailment that necessitates an immediate hospital stay is severe pancreatitis. [12] The male majority of 2.7:1 in this study is consistent with a male preponderance of 4:1 observed in a study conducted in Jamaica. [13]

In order to evaluate the various aetiologies, clinical features, and outcomes of acute pancreatitis, the current study comprised 50 patients who had been diagnosed with the condition. The patients' ages ranged from 24 to 73 years old, with a mean age of 50.96 ± 9.71 years.

There were 20 (40%) female patients and 30 (60%) male patients. Nesvaderani et al. found that the average age of their patients was 50 years old, which is consistent with our findings. [14] The majority of patients in Vengadakrishnan and Koushik's study were between the ages of 21 and 40, in contrast to the current study. Additionally, the mean age of the patients was lower, as reported by Ekka et al., who found that 38 (40%) of the

patients were in their fourth decade of life, with a mean age of 36.14 years. [15, 16] The primary sign of acute pancreatitis is abdominal pain. [11] Seventy-five percent of patients in the study by Sameer et al. at People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhopal, experienced the triad of nausea, vomiting, and epigastric discomfort. [14] In 256 (58.715%) of the cases in our investigation, the triad of nausea, vomiting, and epigastric discomfort was present. All cases had abdominal discomfort, which was consistent with Reid et al.'s study, which found that 96.7% of cases had abdominal pain. In 70.183% of patients, nausea and vomiting were present.

Reid's study conducted in Jamaica yielded similar findings (71.8%). 33.715% of cases had acute fluid collection, which is consistent with findings from studies by Sameer et al. in Bhopal, where 34% of patients had acute fluid collection, and Banday et al. in Jammu, where 36% of patients had it. [12,13] The most frequent systemic consequence (16.5%) was involvement of the respiratory system. This

was consistent with Reid and Raghuvanshi's research. [14] In 82.1% of cases, the disease was mild, and in 4.4% of cases, it was severe. Similar findings were seen in the Ahlawat et al. study conducted in North India, where 82% of patients were categorised as mild. [17] It was discovered that abdominal CT accurately classified 11 of the 13 severe cases, 16 of the 22 moderate cases, and 30 of the 47 light cases. This clearly shows that, due to its lesser sensitivity and the need to prevent needless radiation, CT is more appropriate in severe cases and should not be used in mild or moderate ones. [18] The average length of hospitalization for the patients in this study was 6.89 ± 1.98 days, with a range of 3 to 10 days. Ninety-two percent of the patients were better. 36 (72%) of the individuals in the study experienced no complications from their acute pancreatitis. Four patients (8%), three patients (6%), three patients (6%), one patient (2%), one patient (2%), and two patients (4%) experienced respiratory failure, renal failure, paralytic ileus, pancreatic abscess, and multi-organ failure, respectively. Leucocytosis, comorbidities, and advanced age were predictors of severe pancreatitis, whereas comorbidities, severe pancreatitis, and sequelae were predictors of death in patients with acute pancreatitis. According to Albulushi et al., problems occurred in 9 out of 14 severe cases (64%), compared to 25% in mild cases and 48% in moderate instances. Given that individuals with severe acute pancreatitis had higher morbidities than those with mild and moderate episodes, this order makes sense. [18]

Conclusion

In our study population, the most prevalent presentation was epigastric pain without radiation to the back, while the current published literature strongly supports that this is the most common presentation. The incidence of alcoholic pancreatitis was greater among the cases that were examined. The higher prevalence of alcohol misuse in India explains this. For preventive, lifestyle changes and public education are advised. Our study had a slightly larger proportion of idiopathic pancreatitis than several other studies, which show 10–30%.

References

1. Beger HG, Rau BM. Severe acute pancreatitis: Clinical course and management. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2007; 13(38):5043-51.
2. Beyer G, Hoffmeister A, Michl P, Gress TM, Huber W, Algül H, et al. S3-Leitlinie Pankreatitis e Leitlinie der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Gastroenterologie, Verdauungs- und Stoffwechselkrankheiten (DGVS) e September 2021 e AWMF Registernummer 021-003. *Z Gastroenterol* 2022; 60:419e521.
3. Nesvaderani M, Eslick GD, Vagg D, Faraj S, Cox MR. Epidemiology, aetiology and outcomes of acute pancreatitis: a retrospective cohort study. *Int J Surg Lond Engl* 2015; 23:68e74.
4. Porges T, Shafat T, Sagy I, Schwarzfuchs D, Rahmani Tzvi-Ran I, Jotkowitz A, et al. Clinical characteristics and prognosis of idiopathic acute pancreatitis. *Rambam Maimonides Med J* 2021; 12:e0019.
5. De Beaux AC, Palmer KR, Carter DC. Factors influencing morbidity and mortality in acute pancreatitis; an analysis of 279 cases. *Gut* 1995; 37:121e6.
6. Bai Y, Liu Y, Jia L, Jiang H, Ji M, Lv N, et al. Severe acute pancreatitis in China: etiology and mortality in 1976 patients. *Pancreas* 2007; 35:232e7.
7. Umans DS, Rangkuti CK, Sperna Weiland CJ, Timmerhuis HC, Bouwense SAW, Fockens P, et al. Endoscopic ultrasonography can detect a cause in the majority of patients with idiopathic acute pancreatitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Endoscopy* 2020; 52:955e64.
8. Weitz G, Woitalla J, Wellhoner P, Schmidt K, Büning J, Fellermann K. Does € etiology of acute pancreatitis matter? A review of 391 consecutive episodes. *JOP J Pancreas* 2015; 16:171e5.
9. Trezevant MS, Winton JC, Holmes AK (2019) Hypercalcemia-induced pancreatitis in pregnancy following calcium carbonate ingestion. *J Pharm Pract* 32:225–227
10. Rao BS, Sree Vane M, Chandra VS (2014) Etiology, clinical profile, severity and outcome of acute pancreatitis in relation to bedside index for severity of acute pancreatitis BISAP and CT severity index [CTSI] scores. *Int J Med Res Health Sci* 3:922–928.
11. Orkin SH, Trout AT, Fei L, Lin TK, Nathan JD, Thompson T, Vitale DS (2019) Sensitivity of biochemical and imaging findings for the diagnosis of acute pancreatitis in children. *J Pediatr* 213:143–148 e142.
12. Peery AF, Dellon ES, Lund J, Crockett SD, McGowan CE, Bulsiewicz WJ. Burden of gastrointestinal disease in the United States: 2012 update. *Gastroenterology.* 2012; 143:1179-87.
13. Lee MG, Chung A, Miles A, Terry SI, Royes CA. Chronic pancreatitis in Jamaica. *West Indian Med J.* 1992; 41:61-3.
14. Barreto SG, Tiong L, Williams R. Drug-induced acute pancreatitis in a cohort of 328 patients. A single-centre experience from Australia. *JOP J Pancreas.* 2011; 12(6):581-5.
15. Cappell MS. Acute Pancreatitis: Etiology, Clinical Presentation, Diagnosis, and Therapy. *Med Clin N Am.* 2008; 92:889–923.
16. Raghuvanshi S, Gupta R, Vyas MM, Sharma R. CT Evaluation of Acute Pancreatitis and its

- Prognostic Correlation with CT Severity Index. J Clin Diagnos Res. 2016; 10(6):TC06-11.
17. Ahlawat V, Godara R. Clinical Study of Demographic Profile, Etiology, Severity and Outcome of Acute Pancreatitis in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Northern India. J Gastrointest Dig Syst. 2018; 8:575.
 18. Albulushi A, Siddiqi A, Alqarshoubi I, Aladawi M, Alkhadhour G, Farhan H (2014) Pattern of acute pancreatitis in a tertiary care center in Oman. Oman Med J 29:358.